

On the predictability of possible storylines for forced complex systems

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Abstract. It is well-known that even for fairly simple deterministic nonlinear systems, exact prediction of future state is, on average, impossible beyond some small multiple of the Lyapunov time that quantifies the rate of separation of trajectories within an attractor. Nonetheless, it may be possible to find a physical measure that is the distribution of a trajectory within the attractor. In that sense, there can be a still weaker form of predictability. In this paper, we show that this can also fail but an even weaker form of predictability can appear for non-autonomous (i.e. forced) systems in the presence of tipping points. The *predictability of possible storylines* appears when one can interpret the frequencies of runs within an ensemble arriving at one of several possible future attractors (storylines) in a probabilistic manner. As predictability is a major concern and a challenge in climate science, we illustrate this notion of predictability with two climate-related examples: a chaotic energy balance model and a global ocean model featuring a tipping point of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation.

Keywords: Ensemble prediction | Tipping point | Complex system | Climate forecast

1. Introduction: predictability in complex systems

Complex systems are large disordered systems in which repeated interactions between constituents lead to feedbacks, nonlinearity and emergent properties [1]. They are often out of equilibrium and externally driven. In this paper, we focus on the subset of complex systems that have time-dependent drivers and permit multistable regimes with chaotic attractors or fractal basin boundaries. One can study the behaviour of these systems either through simulation of the underlying processes or through analysis of an equation that approximates the dynamics under given assumptions.

When modelling the dynamics of a complex system, the aim is usually to make predictions about the future state of a system given information about the current state. Palmer [2] quotes Lorenz [3] as pointing out that chaotic behaviour means different levels of predictability may be relevant in different contexts. For a purely deterministic model, one can in principle predict the future of the trajectory x_t (e.g. for an ODE $\dot{x} = f(x)$ where f is some smooth nonlinear function and we write $x_t = \varphi_t(x_0)$ to denote the solution at time $t > 0$) for any given initial condition x_0 . This is solving the initial value problem, referred to as “predictability of the first kind”.

It is well-documented and understood that for deterministic chaos this is not possible in practice beyond some time horizon. Initial uncertainties in x_0 grow exponentially fast at rates given by the Lyapunov exponents until the amplitude of the likely uncertainty of prediction exceeds the size of the attractor. Nonetheless, for typical chaotic attractors with a physical and mixing ergodic measure [4], a typical trajectory x_t that converges to the attractor will have averages determined by some physical invariant measure that is supported on the same attractor, and so averages may be predictable even if the individual trajectory is not. Moreover, this type of convergence would be (subject to being in a particular basin of attraction) independent of initial condition: an initial measure μ_0 (distribution of initial conditions) with a density that is supported in the basin of attraction evolves forward in time as μ_t towards the given attractor. It is reasonable to expect that this measure converges to a physical measure μ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. This is sometimes termed “predictability of the second kind”. More generally, the Palis conjecture [5] states that, for “typical” systems, a “typical” initial condition will evolve towards one of a finite number of attractors, and that moreover, the statistics on each attractor will not depend on the initial condition (for a more precise discussion, see the Materials and Methods) even though the system may be multistable.

Which type of predictability is possible will depend on the timescale considered. For short times, *predictability of trajectory*, where we predict x_t for some future time $t > 0$ given x_0 with small error, is plausible. Over longer times, the weaker notion of *predictability of distribution* may be possible where we predict the statistics of x_t but not the values at specific points in time. Ensemble prediction can explore a range of initial conditions in an attempt to model the distribution of possible states. This sort of predictability of distribution can be verified in simple models such as the Lorenz equations [6]. It is often an implicit assumption that underlies much of simulation-based science that predictability of distribution is possible.

A prototypical example of this is synoptic scale weather [2] which has a predictable trajectory over the timescale of around two weeks. The presence of chaotic fluctuations in atmosphere and ocean flows mean that exact weather predictions over a time horizon of more than this are infeasible, even if the model accuracy and the precision in initial conditions are unrealistically high. Nonetheless, over longer timescales one can reasonably expect predictability of distribution, including time correlation structures over longer timescales. This represents prediction of climate rather than weather and there is a well-developed science of ensemble simulation that has developed over the last

few decades [7, 8]. This is based on simulating a number of likely trajectories with the hope of estimating a distribution of future states.

Although predictability of distribution may be possible in many cases, there are situations where multistability and nonautonomous forcing [9] means this is unachievable. This has been observed in various climate model simulations [10, 11, 12]. In this paper, we argue that in such cases a weaker form of predictability may still be achievable. Starting on a local pullback attractor [13] we say there is *predictability of possible storylines* if there are $N \geq 2$ qualitatively different future attractors (“storylines”) that can be estimated in a probabilistic sense. The probability can be quantified for any particular initial distribution, and for distributions of initial conditions chosen sufficiently far in the past, this converges to a probability $p^{(i)} > 0$ for the i th storyline, independent of the initial distribution. For each of these possible storylines, the asymptotic averages of observables are governed by a measure on that future attractor.

Thus, in the case of forced systems with distinct future attractors, a probabilistic prediction of the future attractor (storyline) is possible, while predictability of distribution is not possible. We illustrate this schematically in Figure 1, via three cases: weak forcing (A), intermediate forcing (B), and strong forcing (C). The weakly forced case (A) behaves as the autonomous (unforced) system - the basins remain stationary meaning there is no mixing between attractors and the future storyline is uniquely predicted by the past state. In the case of intermediate forcing (B), predictability of distribution is no longer possible but there is still predictability of possible storylines for initial conditions associated with the lower attractor. In the case of strong forcing (C), all initial conditions on the lower attractor are shifted to the basin of the upper future attractor - and so the probability of tipping is 1. The upper attractor in the past limit also remains in the basin of the upper future attractor, meaning that effectively all initial conditions in the past are in the basin of the upper (red) future attractor. Nonetheless, observe that for a finite time in the past there can be initial conditions that converge to the lower attractor (blue).

Our notion of predictability of possible storylines suggests that for two or more possible future attractors, the probability of ending up on each attractor is, at least in principle, quantifiable. We show that this form of predictability naturally appears in non-autonomous complex systems, i.e. where there is time-dependent forcing. Suppose that knowledge of the initial state puts us on one of possibly several chaotic pullback/snapshot attractors for a complex autonomous system. In this case, predictability of distribution is possible and there is only one storyline. By contrast, in nonautonomous cases, an ensemble of realisations can split if there is multistability of the final state. This is called “partial tipping” in the terminology of [14, 13]. In this case, predictability of distribution may fail, but predictability of possible storylines can still be achieved.

Predictability of possible storylines differs from the well-studied notion of final state sensitivity and uncertainty exponents discussed in [15] in a number of ways. Final state

Figure 1. Schematic showing three contrasting situations for a time-forced system with two attractors in both past and future limits; some typical trajectories are shown that evolve towards the ellipses which represent the attractors within each time-slice. The blue and red trajectories are assumed to be well mixed within the attractors. The blue shading represents the basin of the lower (blue) attractor in the future. In (A) two nonautonomous attractors remain well separated with predictability of distribution within each. In (B) initial distributions that are pullback attracted to the lower attractor in the past may separate to evolve towards different attractors in the future. Note that in this “partial tipping” situation [13] future basins mix into the lower attractor, meaning that nearby trajectories can have different storylines. There may still be a well-defined probability of each storyline. Not shown: there may be exceptional trajectories that remain on the basin boundary separating the future attractors. In (C) the forcing is such that the predictability of distribution returns, and the lower attractor is only accessible from a set of typical initial conditions that is not achievable in the far past.

sensitivity is relevant for initial conditions in a neighbourhood that is shared between two basins of attraction, in the case where this boundary is fractal. The scaling of the fraction of initial conditions in a small ball that belong to opposite basins is determined as a function of the ball size, and is given by the uncertainty exponent. In that sense, it is a “first order” concept that concerns initial conditions near a basin boundary. In contrast, the predictability of probabilities to follow different future storylines is more of a “zeroth order” concept that concerns an entire basin of attraction (in the pullback sense). The probabilities will be: (a) trivial in the autonomous case or more generally if the pullback and future attractors coincide and (b) constant across the whole of a basin of attraction of a past limit attractor; in other words, the uncertainty fraction is constant, and not a function of ϵ (in the limit $t \rightarrow -\infty$). This corresponds to an uncertainty exponent of 0, unlike the case for a riddled basin where the uncertainty exponent is typically small but positive [16]. For these reasons, we believe that this notion has not been previously identified.

We suggest that this notion of predictability is particularly important in predicting future climate changes. Several components of the climate system are believed to possess

distinct, alternative states, which may be reached when passing climate tipping points. We thus illustrate the breakdown of predictability of distribution but preservation of predictability of storyline with two examples in Section 2. In both examples, we run Monte Carlo simulations of an ensemble of realisations with different initial conditions to explore future storylines. The first example is a global energy balance model of the climate with chaotic natural variability and a temporary forcing by changes in atmospheric CO₂. The second example uses the ocean model Veros to estimate the probability of a permanent shutdown of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) [12] after a temporary overshoot of the tipping point. In Section 3 we give a theoretical justification for predictability of possible storylines for a large class of nonautonomous systems with autonomous limits. This highlights conditions such that probabilities are measurable from ensemble simulations, independent of the details of the ensemble. We finish with a brief discussion of generalizations and open problems in Section 4.

2. Examples with loss of predictability of distribution

2.1. A chaotic global energy balance model

We first consider a global energy balance model (GEBM) of Budyko-Sellers-Ghil type with two stable equilibria subject to forcing through atmospheric CO₂ and natural variability presented in [17], namely

$$C \frac{dT}{dt} = Q_0(1 - \alpha_0(T)) - \varepsilon \sigma T^4 + F_{CO_2}(t) + F_{NV}(t), \quad (1)$$

with C the specific heat capacity, Q_0 the incoming short wave solar radiation, α_0 the mean albedo and $\varepsilon \sigma T^4$ the outgoing long-wave radiation with emissivity ε and Boltzmann constant σ . The term $F_{CO_2}(t)$ represents the mean radiative forcing due to increases in CO₂. Fast timescale changes in temperature due to cloud variability, heat exchange with the ocean, and other factors, are represented by $F_{NV}(t)$, which is modelled as the x -component of a Lorenz-63 model.

More precisely, we consider a simplification of [17] that has constant emissivity and albedo given by:

$$\alpha_0(T) = \alpha_1 + (\alpha_2 - \alpha_1) \frac{1 + \tanh(K_\alpha [T - T_\alpha])}{2} \quad (2)$$

Note that $\alpha_0(T)$ models the lowering of albedo in the presence of land ice sheets. Using [18] we have

$$F_{CO_2}(t) = F_0 + A_0 \log \left[\frac{\rho(t)}{\rho(0)} \right] \quad (3)$$

with $A_0 = 5.35 W m^{-2}$, where $\rho(t)$ is the concentration of atmospheric CO₂ at time t , and F_0 is a reference radiative forcing level for a CO₂ concentration of $\rho(0)$. We include natural variability through a Lorenz-63 model, i.e. natural variability μ_{NV} is given by

$$F_{NV} = \nu_{NV} \sin(\pi x(t)/20). \quad (4)$$

C	5×10^8	$Jm^{-2}K^{-1}$
Q_0	341.3	Wm^{-2}
σ	5.67×10^{-8}	$Wm^{-2}K^{-4}$
α_1	0.6	
α_2	0.52	
T_α	280s	K
K_α	1.0	K^{-1}
ε	0.43	
A_0	5.35	Wm^{-2}
τ_{NV}	6×10^7	s
ν_{NV}	5	Wm^{-2}

Table 1. Parameter values for the chaotic GEBM (1) with used in the numerical simulations. We take the standard choice for the Lorenz parameters: $\sigma = 10$, $\rho = 28$ and $\beta = 8/3$. The forcing F_{CO_2} is given by (3) and F_{NV} represents the amplitude of a chaotic forcing via (4).

where x represents the chaoticity of weather and ocean processes [6]

$$\begin{cases} \tau_{NV} \frac{dx}{dt} = \sigma(y - x) \\ \tau_{NV} \frac{dy}{dt} = x(\rho - z) - y \\ \tau_{NV} \frac{dz}{dt} = xy - \beta z. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Note that ν_{NV} is a measure for the strength of the variability and τ_{NV} is the characteristic timescale of chaotic variability. Parameters are given in Table 1 such that there are two attractors with mean temperature about 14K apart. The nonlinear temperature dependence of albedo means that the model has multiple stable climate states. Figure 2 shows an ensemble of orbits of (1) with an instantaneous quadrupling of CO_2 at $t = 0$ yr and then instantaneous halving of CO_2 at $t = 75$ yr. In other words, we set

$$\rho(t) = \begin{cases} \rho(0) & \text{if } t \leq 0 \\ 4\rho(0) & \text{if } 0 < t \leq 75 \\ 2\rho(0) & \text{if } 75 < t \end{cases} . \quad (6)$$

The orbits are initiated at some point in the past near the low-temperature attractor: Figure 2(A) shows 100 orbits individually, where the ones that tip to the other attractor are shown in red and the others in blue. Figure 2(B) shows the evolution of the probability density over ΔT from 10^6 orbits, with a blue-red colour scale indicating the probability of tipping. The figure indicates that the density of an ensemble of orbits and the probability of tipping to the other attractor are smoothly varying functions of phase space and time. We give a more precise characterization of this in terms of invariant measures and the Palis conjecture for the future limit system in Section 3.

Figure 2. Trajectories of the non-autonomous GE BM (1): Panel (A) shows the response of an ensemble of 100 simulations starting at uniformly placed initial conditions for $t = -100\text{yr}$ to a quadrupling of CO_2 in the period 0 to 75yr and halving thereafter; ΔT denotes the change from the mean temperature before the forcing. The runs that reach $\Delta T > 5$ are shown in red, and the others in blue. Panel (B) shows the marginal probability distribution (vertical axis) for t vs ΔT for the same forcing scenario as in (A), obtained from 10^6 orbits that start on the low-temperature attractor. The probability of tipping to the high-temperature attractor is indicated by a blue (probability 0) to red (probability 1) colour scale.

2.2. Dependence of tipping probability on initial distribution

For the GE BM (1) we present some examples showing that the tipping probability does not depend strongly on initial distribution when started sufficiently far in the past. To this end, Figure 3 shows simulations using a variety of initial ensembles of distribution with the parameters otherwise as in Table 1. There is remarkable consistency in the empirically measured probability of tipping appears to be independent of many of the details of the initial distribution shown.

Ensemble	Initial					size
	x	y	z	T	t	
A	[0, 20]	[0, 20]	[5, 10]	0	-100	500
B	[0, 1]	[0, 1]	[5, 6]	0	-100	500
C	[0, 20]	[0, 20]	[5, 10]	2	-100	500
D	[0, 20]	[0, 20]	[5, 10]	-2	-100	500
E	[0, 20]	[0, 20]	[5, 10]	0	-10	500
F	[0, 20]	[0, 20]	[5, 10]	6	-100	500

Table 2. Parameters governing the initial distributions used for the ensembles shown in Figure 3. An ensemble of the specified size is generated using independent uniformly distributed random choices from the intervals shown.

Figure 3. Non-autonomous GEBM (1) with parameters as in Table 1 and forcing (6) for ensembles (A-F) each of 500 trajectories. The ensembles are initialised as in Table 2. The probability of tipping to the upper attractor is indicated at the top of each panel. Panels (A-E) all agree on tipping probability to within one standard error for a sample of 500 trajectories, even though (E) is started only 10 years before the forcing starts. Panel (F) illustrates what happens when the ensemble starts crossing a basin boundary - only a small fraction of the initial ensemble converges towards the lower attractor meaning that the probability of tipping is far from the other cases. In all cases, the trajectories that arrive at the upper attractor are shown as red, for the lower attractor they are shown as blue.

2.3. AMOC tipping in global ocean model

In our second example we employ the global ocean model Veros [19, 20], which features tipping of the AMOC from a present-day regime of a vigorous circulation to a potential future regime of a collapsed AMOC in response to North Atlantic meltwater increase [21]; see Appendix A for more details. The model displays a rich multistability of co-existing vigorous and collapsed AMOC states, as seen in the bifurcation diagram in Fig. 4(A). Here, symbols of different shape and/or colour correspond to different branches of attractors. It has been shown previously that rate-induced tipping is possible in the model [12], and that predictability of distribution is lost, because chaotic dynamics and partial tipping lead to a sensitive dependence of the asymptotic state on both the initial conditions and the forcing trajectory. Here we illustrate that a breakdown of predictability of distribution also exists in the scenario of a temporary overshoot of the tipping point. To this end, we increase the freshwater forcing to a value $F = F_0 + A$ above the threshold where all vigorous circulation states have lost stability (dashed vertical line in Figure 4(A)), and subsequently decrease it to the original value F_0 (solid vertical line in Figure 4(A)). The time evolution of F is modelled as

$$F(t) = F_0 + \frac{t}{\tau} A e^{1-t/\tau}. \quad (7)$$

The maximum amplitude A of the overshoot is reached at time τ (inset in top right of Figure 4(A)). If A is not too large, and the overshoot and subsequent forcing decrease is fast enough (small τ), the system can avoid tipping and will return to the regime of vigorous AMOC states. If τ is too large, the system will instead transition to one of the branches of collapsed AMOC states that co-exist with the vigorous states at F_0 . Thus, for a given initial condition, the outcome of the overshoot depends on the rate of change of the forcing. This is the case for an overshoot in any system with a tipping point, and similarly, at fixed τ , the outcome of the overshoot will always depend on the initial conditions. When there are chaotic dynamics, as is the case in the ocean model, this dependence is sensitive and there is a loss of predictability of distribution.

Predictability of the outcome of the overshoot scenario is investigated with several ensembles comprising equally spaced initial conditions on a straight line across phase space. The line is defined by one arbitrary sample state on each of the two vigorous AMOC attractors at F_0 . From these two states $\tilde{x}^{(0)}$ and $\tilde{x}^{(1)}$ the initial conditions x_α are defined as

$$x_\alpha = \alpha \tilde{x}^{(0)} + (1 - \alpha) \tilde{x}^{(1)}, \quad (8)$$

where N equally spaced values of α in a certain interval are used.

We begin with ensembles that showcase loss of predictability of distribution. For the first ensemble, we use $N = 64$ values of $\alpha \in [-0.275, 1.3]$. This yields initial conditions that are close to a region around the two attractors, comprising states in both basins. The parameter change is started right away at $t = 0$, such that the system state has not converged onto either of the attractors at the time when the forcing variation begins. We simulate the ensemble for a total of 3,500 years at fixed $\tau = 225$ years, chosen to

Figure 4. (A) Bifurcation diagram of the state of the AMOC in the ocean model Veros with North Atlantic freshwater forcing as control parameter [21]. The inset on the left side is a zoom of the bifurcation diagram close to the eventual AMOC collapse, showcasing the model’s high degree of multistability at different scales. Here we perform an ensemble experiment with a time evolution of the forcing parameter shown in the upper right. Starting at $F=0.3472$ Sv, the freshwater forcing is increased to $F=0.3772$ Sv until time $\tau = 225$ yr, and thereafter decreased again. (B) Time series of the maximum of the Atlantic overturning streamfunction. A total of $N = 180$ simulations are shown, consisting of three ensemble experiments. Realisations that avoid tipping are colored blue, while the ones tipping are shown in red. Time series of long equilibrium simulations on the co-existing attractors are shown in different colors. The inset shows a closeup of the first 200 year of the same ensemble simulations. (C-E) Outcome of three different ensemble experiments, where a black bar for a given realisation indicates that the simulation tipped to an attractor with collapsed AMOC. In panel (D), $N = 64$ initial conditions with values of $\alpha \in [-0.275, 1.3]$ according to (8) were chosen. Panel (C) shows an ensemble of $N = 52$ very closely spaced initial conditions along the same straight line in phase space between realisations 20 and 24 of panel (D). (E) Ensemble as in (D), but all initial conditions have been shifted very slightly by $\alpha \rightarrow \alpha + 0.0025$. (F) Cumulative probability of tipping along the ordered realisations of the ensembles in (D) and (E, red curve).

give roughly equal probability of reaching a vigorous and a collapsed attractor after the overshoot. We find that two out of five possible attractors are reached (Figure 4(B)). For this choice of initial conditions and forcing rate the probability of converging to any other of the five possible attractors seems very low, possibly because the other attractors have a much smaller basin of attraction. Roughly half of the ensemble tips to a collapsed AMOC state, and the other half recovers and converges to a vigorous AMOC attractor. Figure 4(D) shows the outcome of the overshoot experiment, with the individual realisations ordered according to their position on the straight line across phase space. Along the given direction in phase space there is a complicated pattern of tipping and non-tipping initial conditions.

We simulate a second ensemble that is identical to the first one, except that all initial conditions are shifted by a very small amount, corresponding to one tenth of the

Figure 5. (A) Time series of an ensemble with $N = 52$ members with $\alpha \in [0.25, 0.35]$, initialized 1000 years before the forcing variations begin. (B) Zoom-in on the initial 200 years of the simulations. The time series is given as 5-year averages of the AMOC streamfunction maximum. (C) Outcome of the individual realizations.

spacing of initial conditions on the line, such that $\alpha \in [-0.2725, 1.3025]$. The outcome of each ensemble member is shown in Figure 4(E). It can be seen that initial conditions differing only by $d\alpha = 0.0025$, i.e., realisations that are aligned along the vertical axis in Figure 4(D-E), feature only weak correlation in the outcome of overshoot simulation. This shows that even a very small error in the prescription of initial conditions leads to a loss of predictability of the final state, and thus predictability of distribution. However, both ensembles in Figure 4(D-E) adequately quantify the overall probability of tipping for the given interval of initial conditions, and arrive at the exact same number of tipping realisations (33 out of 64), corresponding to a cumulative probability at the final ensemble member of 0.515625 (Figure 4(F)). This is coincidental to some degree, since the cumulative probabilities calculated over only parts of the ensemble differ somewhat. Both ensembles seem to capture variations of the tipping probability in phase space [13], with a generally higher density of tipping trajectories in the first half of realisations. Indeed, the ensemble separates qualitatively within the first 50 years such that most realisations that start with a lower AMOC strength end up tipping (coloured time series in inset of Figure 4(B)).

The probability of tipping obtained by the first two ensembles is likely not robust, since the collection of initial conditions cross a basin boundary. Zooming in on a more narrow region of phase space that does not contain a basin boundary, we perform another ensemble of $N = 52$ members with $\alpha \in [0.25, 0.35]$ (Figure 4(C)). Again there is a seemingly random pattern of tipping and non-tipping realizations, indicating loss of final state predictability. The overall probability of tipping is 0.451, which is reasonably close to the one previously obtained, despite the much restricted range of initial conditions.

In the ocean model ensembles presented so far the initial conditions were chosen close to an attractor, but no additional time was given for orbits to converge to it

before the forcing change. In this case we expect the probabilities of the individual storylines to depend on the initial conditions, and to be generally different from the probabilities obtained when all ensemble members had sufficient time to relax to the attractor. If the ensemble is initiated sufficiently long before the forcing change, and given that all initial conditions are chosen within the same basin of attraction of a past limit attractor, we expect much less dependence of the probabilities of storylines on the chosen initial conditions distribution. To this end, another ensemble is performed with the same small range of initial conditions within one basin with $\alpha \in [0.25, 0.35]$, but where the simulations begin at $t = -1000$ years while the forcing variation starts at $t = 0$ years. The results are shown in Fig. 5. The probability of tipping is significantly smaller at $P = 0.196$. The initial spread in AMOC strength is about 0.1 Sv, and after about a century the realizations seem uncorrelated (Fig. 5(B)), indicating that the time period before the forcing variation is clearly larger than the time scale of mixing on the attractor.

It will be interesting to explore further whether the conditions are such that the tipping probability estimated from this ensemble reflects that expected by sampling the physical measure on the past pullback attractor.

3. Probability of tipping and physical measures

The examples in Section 2 illustrate scenarios where predicting the outcome of a single realisation is impossible, while it is still possible to predict the probability of reaching a specific attractor and the limiting distribution over attractors for an ensemble of initial conditions. Here, we formulate this in general terms. We focus on a class of nonautonomous dynamical systems on $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = f(x, t) \text{ where } f(x, t) \rightarrow f_{\pm}(x) \text{ as } t \rightarrow \pm\infty \quad (9)$$

that are asymptotically autonomous[‡] in the past and future limits. Note that $f_+(x)$ and $f_-(x)$ may be the same or different systems. We assume that the Palis conjecture holds for f_+ , namely it has a finite number of attractors $\{A_i\}_{i=1}^N$ with $N \geq 2$ and these attract in a way that typical trajectories behave asymptotically in a similar way (see Appendix B).

Equation (9) determines the evolution of a single orbit. To show predictability of possible storylines, we need to consider the evolution of an ensemble of orbits starting at an initial distribution with density $\rho_{t_0} = \rho_{t_0}(x)$. Note that given any initial distribution with a density, the limiting distribution may be singular with respect to Lebesgue measure – it is no longer a density. For the exposition here we assume that it is, if necessary substituting the original system by an approximation on a discrete phase space.

[‡] More precisely, suppose there is an open bounded set M that contains all forward orbits and such that $\sup_{x \in M} |f(x, t) - f_{\pm}(x)| \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \pm\infty$. For the strongest results, it may be necessary to assume that this convergence is sufficiently rapid [22].

3.1. Decomposition into asymptotic states

The probability distribution of an ensemble as a function of time is governed by the equation

$$\rho_t(x) = (\mathcal{P}_{(t_0,t)}\rho_{t_0})(x). \quad (10)$$

Here, $\mathcal{P}_{(t_0,t)}$ is the transfer operator (also Perron–Frobenius operator), where t_0, t indicate that it is associated with the map $\varphi_{(t_0,t)}$ that maps solutions of f between t_0 and t .

We are interested in what happens for $t \rightarrow \infty$. Suppose we start at time t_0 with an ensemble of orbits that are on a single attractor of f_- . In the $t \rightarrow \infty$ limit of ρ_t , the ensemble will be split between different attractors of f_+ . The relative frequency of orbits on parts of a given attractor is then determined by the invariant distribution on the attractor. Each invariant distribution is weighted by the total mass that ends up on its attractor. These considerations imply that ρ_∞ can be written as

$$\rho_\infty(x) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sum_i^N \pi_+^{(i)}(x) \int_{A_i} (\mathcal{P}_{(t_0,t)}\rho_{t_0})(x') dx', \quad (11)$$

where $\pi_+^{(i)}(x)$ is the invariant distribution on attractor i of f_+ . Because ρ_{t_0} starts on a single attractor, we can define the tipping probability to any attractor of f_+ as

$$\begin{aligned} P(x_\infty \in A_i | \rho_{t_0}) &= \int_{A_i} \rho_\infty(x) dx, \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int_{A_i} \sum_i^N \pi_+^{(i)}(x) dx \int_{A_i} (\mathcal{P}_{(t_0,t)}\rho_{t_0})(x') dx', \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int_{A_i} (\mathcal{P}_{(t_0,t)}\rho_{t_0})(x') dx', \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where the invariant probability measures are normalised. Using (12), we can rewrite (11) as

$$\rho_\infty(x) = \sum_i^N \pi_+^{(i)}(x) P(x_\infty \in A_i | \rho_{t_0}). \quad (13)$$

This shows that the asymptotic probability distribution starting at some past attractor (a physical measure on a pullback attractor [13]) is a weighted average of the invariant probability measures. The weights are determined by the tipping probabilities, which in turn depend on f and ρ_{t_0} . If ρ_{t_0} is supported in the basin of a chaotic mixing attractor of f_- , ρ_{t_0} will converge weakly to a physical measure π_- as $t_0 \rightarrow -\infty$, meaning that the tipping probability from ρ_{t_0} to A_i will asymptotically no longer depend on t_0 and we can write the conditional probability in (13) as $p^{(i)}$ and

$$\rho_\infty(x) = \sum_i^N \pi_+^{(i)}(x) p^{(i)}. \quad (14)$$

where the probability of tipping to the future attractor A_i is

$$p^{(i)} = P(x_\infty \in A_i | \pi_-). \quad (15)$$

These considerations are verifiable under some reasonable assumptions, namely if the Palis conjecture holds for the future limit system, and if a zero measure subset of the physical measure on the pullback attractor ends up on a basin boundary in future - we refer to [13, Theorem 6] for a context where a precise statement can be proven.

In the special case where the time dependence is due to switching between different autonomous systems, where f_- acts on $t \in (-\infty, 0)$, f_1 on $t \in [0, \theta)$, and f_+ on $t \in [\theta, \infty)$, the probability distribution evolves as

$$\rho_t(x) = \begin{cases} (\mathcal{P}_1^k \pi_-)(x) & \text{if } t = k\Delta t \in [0, \theta), \\ (\mathcal{P}_+^{k-n} \mathcal{P}_1^n \pi_-)(x) & \text{if } t = k\Delta t \geq \theta = n\Delta t. \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Here, we assumed that the ensemble has settled on a single attractor of f_- by $t = 0$, with invariant probability measure $\pi_-(x)$. $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_+$ are the transfer operators of f_1, f_+ , where their associated maps have time step $\Delta t = \theta/n$, with $n \in \mathbb{N}$. An example of this case is the energy balance model above, where $\theta = 75\text{yr}$. The limiting probability distribution can be obtained either via the above procedure, or, alternatively, by considering the state at $t = \theta$. At $t = \theta$, $\mathcal{P}_1^n \pi_-$ works as initial distribution for f_+ . The part of $\mathcal{P}_1^n \pi_-$ that has settled on an attractor will stay there. The part that is still transient has, for each i , a probability q_i of ending on attractor i of f_+ . Integrating separately over the attractors and transient parts, we obtain

$$\rho_\infty(x) = \sum_i^N \pi_+^{(i)}(x) \left[\int_{A_i} (\mathcal{P}_1^n \pi_-)(x') dx' + \right. \quad (17)$$

$$\left. \int_{\mathcal{B}(A_i) \setminus A_i} (\mathcal{P}_1^n \pi_-)(x') q_i(x') dx' \right]. \quad (18)$$

Knowing that $q_i(x) = 1$ for $x \in A_i$, one can simplify this as

$$\rho_\infty(x) = \sum_i^N \pi_+^{(i)}(x) \int_{\mathcal{B}(A_i)} (\mathcal{P}_1^n \pi_-)(x') q_i(x') dx', \quad (19)$$

where the integral can be replaced with the tipping probability $p^{(i)}$ as before.

Note that one could implement the piecewise autonomous case numerically by partitioning phase space into boxes, such that the probability of being in a box evolves as a Markov chain [23]. Each transfer operator $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_+$ then corresponds to a Markov matrix P_1, P_+ . Each attractor A_i corresponds to a recurrent class of P_+ , while $\mathcal{B}(A_i) \setminus A_i$ corresponds to the transient classes connecting to this recurrent class. The invariant probability measures correspond to the invariant distributions of the recurrent classes.

3.2. Estimating ensembles that give the same prediction

Suppose we start an ensemble ρ_{t_0} of initial conditions at time t_0 that are centred around some initial state x_0 and with diameter ϵ_0 . The assumption that the probability of a possible future storyline is independent of a particular ensemble will be valid if the ensemble ρ samples the ‘‘physical measure’’ in an unbiased way. For this to be the case, we need to look at the rate at which the ensemble approaches the attractor, and

how fast it is mixed into the attractor, as well as how close the system is to the past asymptotic state. These timescales may be quite varied and *a priori* hard to estimate. However, they can be used to give a ballpark figure of when the ensemble will faithfully sample the physical measure, given an accurate estimate of the tipping probability even for randomly chosen ensembles not far from onset of forcing; see Figure 3.

Let us assume that the timescale of attraction of an ensemble of size ϵ_0 starting near x_0 at time t_0 to a neighbourhood of the past attractor is t_a , the timescale of mixing on the attractor is t_m and the system diverges away from the past limit system (i.e. the forcing starts) at around time t_1 . One can expect the ensemble to faithfully sample the physical measure if

$$\epsilon_0 \exp \left[\frac{t_1 + t_a - t_0}{t_m} \right] \gg 1. \quad (20)$$

This means we can expect an estimate of the tipping probabilities that is broadly independent of the details of the ensemble if the following hold:

- The mixing is rapid, i.e. the timescale of mixing t_m is not too large;
- The diameter of the initial ensemble is large enough, i.e. ϵ_0 is not too tiny;
- The initial distribution is not too far from the attractor, i.e. t_a is not too large;
- The system is started sufficiently far in the past; i.e. $t_1 - t_0$ is not too small.

There is a trade-off of these individual points, implied by (20). For instance, due to the exponential dependence on the inverse mixing time scale, even a very small ϵ_0 can in principle give a very good sampling of the physical measure.

The above statements are conservative because there is also time for mixing and attraction to the pullback attractor during the non-autonomous part of the forcing scenario, before a threshold is reached that separates tipping from non-tipping realisations. This threshold may depend in a complicated way on the system and the forcing scenario, and it is thus difficult to give general statements on the relevant time scale. But it nevertheless means that there can be independence of the tipping probabilities on ensemble details, even if the ensemble is initialised only very shortly before the forcing starts. This appears to be the case for the simulations in Figure 3(E), where the ensemble is initialised only a short time before the forcing variation, which is smaller than the mixing and attraction time scales. It is an interesting challenge to explore this more systematically, to better quantify the trade-offs between the various reasons an ensemble may fail to give a consistent tipping probability.

4. Discussion

In this paper we consider cases where predictability of distribution is lost and, due to forcing, an ensemble simulation started near one attractor splits into distinct future attractors (i.e. storylines). Nonetheless, we argue that the relative abundance of each scenario may still be faithfully interpreted as the probability of a possible storyline. Although both of the examples discussed here are models arising in climate science, we

note that the concepts discussed here will be of potential relevance in a wide range of application areas where there is nonstationary forcing and multistability. Moreover, the details of the model do not need to be known explicitly - the results should be applicable to ensemble simulations of models that are data-derived (eg [24]) as long as they are sufficiently complex.

Loss of predictability of distribution is not possible for a purely autonomous or weakly/slowly forced system initialised in the basin of a single attractor. It requires multistability, a chaotic attractor in the past limit, and significant forcing. It can occur as a result of partial tipping [13] from an attractor of a nonautonomous system for intermediate levels of forcing. The Palis conjecture suggests that (up to a set of zero Lebesgue measure in phase space) only a finite number of storylines are possible in the future. This means that the possible storylines can be explored effectively by Monte Carlo simulations - although exceptional behaviour such as unstable periodic orbits within attractors may be present, we can discount realizations limiting to such “pathological” trajectories from any random ensemble with probability one. We verified that this is the case in our two examples. More precisely, suppose there is a physical measure on a pullback attractor [13] and this becomes distributed across the basins of several attractors in the future. In that case, this will imply a loss of predictability of distribution but can still give the weaker predictability of possible storylines with a fixed probability. We caution that the existence of such a physical measure on a pullback attractor may seem plausible in general, but it has only been rigorously proven in special cases [22].

Over what timescales can one get predictability of various kinds? This is particularly relevant for complex systems such as the climate system whose components can evolve at vastly differing timescales. In such cases, the predictability of possible storylines will depend on which slow processes are included - for example, simulations that include ocean dynamics can show extremely long timescales of relaxation to a final attractor [25] and can include cases of “late tipping” [17]. Generally speaking, a variety of timescales will be important, as discussed in Section 3.2; some of these may be obvious but others may be more subtly defined and more challenging to understand.

In this paper we highlight that a loss of predictability of distribution may be a robust feature of forced (nonautonomous) systems where an ensemble is started on a “past limit attractor” and there is splitting of the ensemble. The latter may be either due to a temporary overshoot of a tipping point [26], or for other reasons of rapid time-varying forcing, where in certain systems a monotonic parameter shift can take typical conditions and leave them near basin boundaries (rate-induced tipping). Loss of predictability of distribution occurs when there is ensemble splitting starting from a chaotic past limit attractor. In contrast, there can be ensemble splitting with no loss of predictability of distribution when the past limit attractor is a limit cycle and there are no fractal basin boundaries or chaotic saddles. Note that loss of predictability of distribution applies both for cases of a fixed forcing trajectory and uncertainty in initial conditions, and of fixed initial conditions but uncertainty in the forcing trajectory [12].

For unforced systems, an ensemble that contains initial conditions in several basins of attraction can also split in a complicated manner owing to fractal basin boundaries between these attractors and there may be some mixing of ensemble trajectory fates due to this, rather than due to chaos in the attractors.

It is sometimes assumed that complex systems in sufficiently high dimensions will not exhibit multistability [27]. This belief is reinforced by the observation that for many commonly used forms of noise (eg Wiener process noise), unboundedness of stochastic variations will defeat multistability in the long term. However, bistability and multistability do exist in many models of interest, ranging from complex networks of coupled systems [28] to climate models [29]. In such cases, the predictability of possible storylines should help interpret situations giving a variety of possible outcomes.

Finally, we note that different model forms of the same complex system may have different types of predictability, depending on which features are included or excluded. For example, a mean-field ODE approximation of a cellular automaton (or agent-based) predator-prey system will not exhibit chaos, while spatial models can have regimes with chaos [30]. Hence, in this case, the spatial models have predictability of distribution (or of storylines if there are coexisting chaotic attractors), while the ODE model has predictability of trajectory.

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Appendix A. Global ocean model Veros

We employ the primitive equation finite-difference global ocean model *Veros* [19, 20], where mesoscale turbulence is represented using the Redi [31] and Gent-McWilliams [32] parameterization for isopycnal and thickness diffusion (diffusivity of 1,000 m²/s). The second order turbulence closure of Gaspar et al. [33] is used to account for diapycnal mixing. The heat exchange boundary condition is expressed by a first-order Taylor expansion of the heat flux as a function of the anomaly of the modeled surface temperature with respect to a fixed surface temperature climatology [34]. For this, we use ERA-40 climatologies [35] of surface temperature and heat flux, as well as a climatology of the derivative of the heat flux with respect to changes in surface ocean temperature. Wind stress forcing is also taken from ERA-40. Freshwater exchanges with the atmosphere are modeled by boundary conditions under which the sea surface salinity is relaxed towards a present-day ERA-40 climatological field within a given relaxation timescale. By choosing a long timescale of 2 years, oceanic salinity anomalies are less efficiently damped by the atmospheric forcing compared to temperature anomalies. This enables the positive salt advection feedback, which can lead to AMOC multi-stability and tipping.

The bathymetry is obtained by smoothing the ETOPO1 global relief model [36] with a Gaussian filter to match the grid resolution. The model domain ends at 80°N and thereby does not feature an Arctic connection of ocean basins. The horizontal grid contains 90 longitudinal and 40 latitudinal cells, where the latitudinal resolution increases from 5.3° at the poles to 2.1° at the Equator, as well as 40 vertical layers, which increase in thickness from 23 m at the surface to 274 m at the bottom. For further model details, see our previous studies that investigated AMOC tipping in this ocean model [12, 37, 21].

Appendix B. A note on the Palis conjecture and predictability of storylines

Consider a system modelled by an autonomous flow $x_t = \varphi_t(x_0)$ where for convenience we assume boundedness of forward orbits. The Palis conjecture [5] states that for typical systems, there will be a finite number N of attractors A_i such that the Lebesgue measure of the phase space is exhausted by the basins of a suitable set of attractors:

$$\ell \left(\mathbb{R}^d \setminus \bigcup_i \mathcal{B}(A_i) \right) = 0$$

where $\mathcal{B}(A) = \{x_0 : d(\varphi_t(x_0), A) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } t \rightarrow \infty\}$ is the basin of attraction and $d(x, A) = \inf_{y \in A} d(x, y)$ measures the distance of the point x to the set A . The conjecture states in addition that each of these attractors A_i supports a unique physical measure $\mu^{(i)}$ [4]. This is an ergodic invariant measure that determines the frequency of visiting regions of the attractor, and that hence determines the value of averaged observables.

Note that this conjecture implies that for each i and any continuous observable $g : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the average converges:

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_{t=0}^T g(\varphi_t(x_0)) dt = \int g(x) d\mu^{(i)}(x) \quad (\text{B.1})$$

for all except for a set of $x_0 \in \mathcal{B}(A_i)$ with Lebesgue measure zero. Hence properties such as Lyapunov exponents of an attractor depend only on the attractor. Unless the initial condition is for example on a basin boundary.

The Palis conjecture has so far been proven only in quite limited low dimensional cases [38] such as where the attractors are uniformly hyperbolic or even equilibrium. There are cases where it does not hold such as for Newhouse’s result [39] on infinite number of sinks that can appear - see for example [40], implying an infinite number of attractors, or non-ergodic attractors that may appear in special case [41]. However, these are in some sense pathological cases and an implicit assumption is made in most numerically based studies that the Palis conjecture holds. We are not aware of an equivalent to the Palis conjecture for nonautonomous systems, but if the future limit of a system such as (9) satisfies the Palis conjecture then it seems very reasonable to assume that nonautonomous invariant measures will be “shared out” between the attractors in the future limit.

References

- [1] James Ladyman and Karoline Wiesner. *What is a complex system?* Yale University Press, 2020.
- [2] T N Palmer. Predicting uncertainty in forecasts of weather and climate. *Reports on Progress in Physics*, 63(2):71, feb 2000.
- [3] E N Lorenz. Climatic predictability. *GARP Publications series*, pages 132–136, 1975.
- [4] Lai-Sang Young. What are SRB measures, and which dynamical systems have them? *Journal of Statistical Physics*, 108:733–754, 2002.
- [5] Jacob Palis. A global view of dynamics and a conjecture on the denseness of finitude of attractors. *Asterisque*, 261(xiiiiv):335–347, 2000.
- [6] Edward N Lorenz. Deterministic nonperiodic flow. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 20(2):130 – 141, 1963.
- [7] Antje Weisheimer, Damien Decremet, David MacLeod, Christopher O’Reilly, Tim N Stockdale, Stephanie Johnson, and Tim N Palmer. How confident are predictability estimates of the winter North Atlantic Oscillation? *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 145:140–159, 2019.
- [8] M Milleer. Stochastic representation of model uncertainties in the ECMWF ensemble prediction system. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 125(560):2887–2908, 1999.
- [9] Michael Ghil and Valerio Lucarini. The physics of climate variability and climate change. *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 92:035002, Jul 2020.
- [10] Valerio Lucarini and Tamás Bódai. Edge states in the climate system: exploring global instabilities and critical transitions. *Nonlinearity*, 30:R32–R66, 2017.
- [11] Bálint Kaszás, Tímea Haszpra, and Mátyás Herein. The snowball Earth transition in a climate model with drifting parameters: Splitting of the snapshot attractor. *Chaos*, 29:113102, 2019.
- [12] Johannes Lohmann and Peter D Ditlevsen. Risk of tipping the overturning circulation due to increasing rates of ice melt. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(9):e2017989118, 2021.

- [13] Peter Ashwin and Julian Newman. Physical invariant measures and tipping probabilities for chaotic attractors of asymptotically autonomous systems. *The European Physical Journal Special Topics*, 230(16):3235–3248, 2021.
- [14] Hassan M Alkhayouon and Peter Ashwin. Rate-induced tipping from periodic attractors: Partial tipping and connecting orbits. *Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science*, 28(3), 2018.
- [15] Celso Grebogi, Steven W. McDonald, Edward Ott, and James A. Yorke. Final state sensitivity: An obstruction to predictability. *Physics Letters A*, 99(9):415–418, 1983.
- [16] Edward Ott and JC Alexander. The transition to chaotic attractors with riddled basins. *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena*, 76(4):384–410, 1994.
- [17] Robbin Bastiaansen, Peter Ashwin, and Anna S von der Heydt. Climate response and sensitivity: time scales and late tipping points. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A*, 479(2269):20220483, 2023.
- [18] G Myhre, D Shindell, F-M Bréon, W Collins, J Fuglestedt, J Huang, D Koch, Lamargue J-F, D Lee, B Mendoza, T Nakajima, A Robock, G Stephens, T Takemura, and H Zhang. Antropogenic and natural radiative forcing. In T F Stocker, D Qin, G-K Plattner, M Tignor, S K Allen, J Boschung, A Nauels, Y Xia, V Bex, and P M Midgley, editors, *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report on the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, chapter 8, pages 659–740. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 2013.
- [19] Dion Häfner, René L Jacobsen, Carsten Eden, Mads R B Kristensen, Markus Jochum, Roman Nuterman, and Brian Vinter. Veros v0.1 – a fast and versatile ocean simulator in pure python. *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 11:3299–3312, 2018.
- [20] Dion Häfner, Roman Nuterman, and Markus Jochum. Fast, cheap, and turbulent—global ocean modeling with gpu acceleration in Python. *JAMES*, 13:e2021MS002717, 2021.
- [21] Johannes Lohmann, Henk A Dijkstra, Markus Jochum, Valerio Lucarini, and Peter D Ditlevsen. Multistability and intermediate tipping of the Atlantic Ocean Circulation. *Sci. Adv.*, 10:eadi4253, 2024.
- [22] Julian Newman and Peter Ashwin. Physical measures of asymptotically autonomous dynamical systems. *Stochastics and Dynamics*, page 2350020, 2023.
- [23] Michael Dellnitz, Gary Froyland, and Oliver Junge. The algorithms behind GAIO—set oriented numerical methods for dynamical systems. In *Ergodic theory, analysis, and efficient simulation of dynamical systems*, pages 145–174. Springer, 2001.
- [24] Remi Lam, Alvaro Sanchez-Gonzalez, Matthew Willson, Peter Wirnsberger, Meire Fortunato, Ferran Alet, Suman Ravuri, Timo Ewalds, Zach Eaton-Rosen, Weihua Hu, Alexander Merose, Stephan Hoyer, George Holland, Oriol Vinyals, Jacklynn Stott, Alexander Pritzel, Shakir Mohamed, and Peter Battaglia. Learning skillful medium-range global weather forecasting. *Science*, 382(6677):1416–1421, 2023.
- [25] Syukuro Manabe and Ronald J Stouffer. Century-scale effects of increased atmospheric CO₂ on the ocean–atmosphere system. *Nature*, 364(6434):215–218, 1993.
- [26] Paul Ritchie, Özkan Karabacak, and Jan Sieber. Inverse-square law between time and amplitude for crossing tipping thresholds. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A*, 475(2222):20180504, 2019.
- [27] Bo Christiansen. Analysis of ensemble mean forecasts: The blessings of high dimensionality. *Monthly Weather Review*, 147(5):1699 – 1712, 2019.
- [28] Stefano Boccaletti, Vito Latora, Yamir Moreno, Martin Chavez, and D-U Hwang. Complex networks: Structure and dynamics. *Physics Reports*, 424(4-5):175–308, 2006.
- [29] Georgios Margazoglou, Tobias Grafke, Alessandro Laio, and Valerio Lucarini. Dynamical landscape and multistability of a climate model. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 477(2250):20210019, 2021.
- [30] J A Sherratt, M A Lewis, and A C Fowler. Ecological chaos in the wake of invasion. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 92(7):2524–2528, 1995.

- [31] Martha H Redi. Oceanic isopycnal mixing by coordinate rotation. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, 12:1154–1158, 1982.
- [32] Peter R Gent and James C McWilliams. Isopycnal mixing in ocean circulation models. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, 20:150–155, 1990.
- [33] Philippe Gaspar, Yves Grégoris, and Jean-Michel Lefevre. A simple eddy kinetic energy model for simulations of the oceanic vertical mixing: Tests at station papa and long-term upper ocean study. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 95:16179–16193, 1990.
- [34] Bernard Barnier. *Forcing the oceans*, pages 45–80. Springer, 1998.
- [35] Sakari M Uppala et al. The ERA-40 re-analysis. *Q. J. Roy. Meteor. Soc.*, 131:2961–3012, 2005.
- [36] C Amante. Etopo1, global 1 arc-minute global relief model: Procedures, data sources and analysis. *NOAA Tech. Memo. NESDIS NGDC-24*, page 19, 2009.
- [37] Johannes Lohmann and Anders Svensson. Ice core evidence for major volcanic eruptions at the onset of Dansgaard–Oeschger warming events. *Clim Past*, 18:2021–2043, 2022.
- [38] Jacek Graczyk and Grzegorz Swiatek. Generic hyperbolicity in the logistic family. *Annals of Mathematics*, 146(1):1–52, 1997.
- [39] Sheldon E Newhouse. The abundance of wild hyperbolic sets and non-smooth stable sets for diffeomorphisms. *Publications Mathématiques de l’IHÉS*, 50:101–151, 1979.
- [40] Laura Tedeschini-Lalli and James A Yorke. How often do simple dynamical processes have infinitely many coexisting sinks? *Communications in Mathematical Physics*, 106(4):635–657, 1986.
- [41] Özkan Karabacak and Peter Ashwin. On statistical attractors and the convergence of time averages. *Mathematical Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, 150(2):353–365, 2011.